

Barnard's Syndrome: Biliary Ileus Secondary to Bilioenteric Fistula. Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Biliary ileus is a rare cause of intestinal obstruction, first described by Bartholin in 1654, is an impaction of gallstones into the intestinal tract through a cholecystoenteric fistula (CEF). A CEF, a relatively rare complication of gallstones, is defined as an autonomous communication between the inflamed gallbladder and the surrounding adherent gastrointestinal tract, usually secondary to Mirizzi's syndrome. Computed tomography (CT), with a sensitivity greater than 90% and specificity close to 100%. The treatment of biliary ileus is surgical and is mainly aimed at resolving the intestinal obstruction, the optimal surgical approach is still under debate. There are mainly 3 current surgical options: isolated enterotomy with spontaneous closure of the fistula, one-stage surgery performing enterolithotomy with cholecystectomy and closure of the fistula, and lastly two-stage surgery consisting of enterolithotomy followed by cholecystectomy and closure of the fistula.

KEYWORDS: biliary, ileus, cholecystoenteric, fistula

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INTRODUCTION

Biliary ileus is a rare cause of intestinal obstruction, first described by Bartholin in 1654, is an impaction of gallstones into the intestinal tract through a cholecystoenteric fistula (CEF). In 1940 the London Medical Gazette published the first cholecystoduodenal (cholecystoenteric) fistula, which is responsible for 1% to 4% of all mechanical intestinal obstructions (1, 2).

Biliary ileus occurs in 0.3% to 0.5% of all patients with gallstones. The most frequent location in 50 to 90% of cases is in the terminal ileum, Barnard's syndrome most commonly affects the terminal ileum or ileocecal valve, in 3% of cases the stone is located in the duodenum and blocks the gastric outlet, which is known as Bouveret's syndrome, and less than 4.8% of patients present obstruction in the colon. It usually occurs in people over 60 years of age, predominantly in women. Most impacted gallstones measure more than 2.5 cm, usually between 2 and 5 cm (3, 4, 5).

A CEF, a relatively rare complication of gallstones, is defined as an autonomous communication between the inflamed gallbladder and the surrounding adherent gastrointestinal tract, usually secondary to Mirizzi's syndrome. The most frequent place where fistulas form is between the gallbladder and the duodenum, representing 85% of all types. The other 15% are hepatoduodenal, choledochoduodenal, cholecystogastric, cholecystojejunal and cholecystocolonic fistulas (4, 6).

Bilioenteric disorders are usually asymptomatic, with the presence of an insidious and very nonspecific clinical picture. The clinical presentation of biliary ileus can be acute: abdominal distension, vomiting and constipation; subacute: there are no bowel movements but it does channel gases (low-grade intestinal obstruction); chronic or Karewsky's syndrome: recurrent episodes of abdominal pain caused by the passage of gallstones through the intestine, alternating with an asymptomatic period until reaching complete obstruction (7, 8, 9). In the case of Barnard's syndrome, which refers to stones blocking the ileocecal valve, it may present as a typical

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intestinal obstruction, sometimes accompanied by jaundice (less than 15%), manifesting as abdominal distension, pain, vomiting, absence of peristalsis, constipation (3).

Preoperative diagnosis is achieved by imaging studies, such as ultrasound which can be used to visualize fistulas, pneumobilia, impacted gallstones and residual cholelithiasis or common bile duct stones, but the difficulty in localizing the stones and the interference with intestinal gas make this study less effective. Computed tomography (CT), with a sensitivity greater than 90% and specificity close to 100%, should be performed upon clinical suspicion; findings compatible with biliary ileus are gallbladder thickening, pneumobilia, intestinal obstruction and obstructive gallstones. MRI could be used as a potential adjunct to accurately define the anatomy of the fistula. Other studies such as gastroscopy or colonoscopy may be useful to visualize the fistula (9, 10).

Abdominal radiography has a sensitivity of 40-70%. The imaging diagnostic criterion for biliary ileus is called Rigler's triad in less than 30% and consists of the presence of radiopaque calculi (occurring in less than 10% of cases), pneumobilia (Gotta-Mentschler sign), and distension of the intestinal loops. The presence of 2 of the 3 signs establishes the diagnosis.

The treatment of biliary ileus is surgical and is mainly aimed at resolving the intestinal obstruction, the optimal surgical

approach is still under debate. There are mainly 3 current surgical options: isolated enterotomy with spontaneous closure of the fistula, one-stage surgery performing enterolithotomy with cholecystectomy and closure of the fistula, and lastly two-stage surgery consisting of enterolithotomy followed by cholecystectomy and closure of the fistula (10, 11, 12).

CASE REPORT

A 56-year-old male, with no hereditary or surgical history, with long-standing untreated diabetes. He comes to the emergency department with a current condition of five days of evolution characterized by moderate intensity colicky abdominal pain in the right hypochondrium, which does not yield to analgesia, nausea, abdominal distension and decrease in the caliber of stool. On physical examination, pain on superficial and deep palpation in the right hypochondrium, peristalsis present, tympanic, with no evidence of peritoneal irritation. Laboratory tests were requested, reporting mild leukocytosis and hydroelectrolyte alterations.

A simple abdominal X-ray was requested, showing scarce hydro-aerial levels and distension of intestinal loops (Figure 1), so the patient was referred to the General Surgery Department with a diagnosis of probable intestinal obstruction.

Figure 1: Plain abdominal X-ray, showing hydro-aerial levels and distension of intestinal loops, probably due to intestinal obstruction.

A CT scan was requested showing intestinal obstruction caused by impaction of a probable gallstone (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Simple tomography of the abdomen. 2A: Cross section with small bowel dilatation. 2B: Coronal section with transition site between distal ileum and ascending colon, indicating obstruction by probable foreign body.

A likely biliary ileus was diagnosed. Exploratory laparotomy was performed, intestinal loops were explored from the treitz angle to the ileocecal valve, identifying a foreign body in the distal ileum adjacent to the ileocecal valve, a longitudinal enterotomy of approximately 5 cm was performed and calculus

was extracted, then the enterotomy was closed in two planes, the first with Connell-Mayo stitches using 3-0 polyglycolic acid suture, and cushioning type seromuscular stitches with 3-0 non-absorbable silk suture (Figure 3).

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Figure 3. A. Enterotomy (longitudinal incision), emptying of the distal bowel and removal of the calculus. B. Closure of the bowel. C. Gallstone removed from the small bowel.

The surgical findings were: distended small bowel loops, 6 x 4 cm oval calculus, bilioenteric fistula, palpable induration at the level of the gallbladder neck and first portion of the duodenum. Gallbladder with no evidence of acute inflammation. The patient was hospitalized for 5 days, with clinical improvement and was discharged with outpatient follow-up for 3 months, persisting asymptomatic.

DISCUSSION

Barnard's syndrome represents a rare and complex form of biliary ileus, characterized by the impaction of a gallstone in the ileocecal valve, which generates mechanical intestinal obstruction (1, 2).

Although the incidence of biliary ileus is low (0.3% to 0.5% in patients with cholelithiasis), it is responsible for only 1% to 4% of all mechanical intestinal obstructions, its incidence increases in elderly patients with a history of chronic cholecystitis. (2, 4) This syndrome arises mainly from a bilioenteric fistula, which in most cases is formed between the gallbladder and duodenum due to chronic inflammation or Mirizzi's syndrome. (4, 6) The formation of this abnormal communication allows the passage of large gallstones into the gastrointestinal tract, predisposing to intestinal obstruction when the stone is impacted in anatomically narrow areas, such as the ileocecal valve.(3, 4)

In the present case, the patient presented with nonspecific symptoms, such as abdominal pain, nausea, abdominal distension and changes in bowel habit. These findings reflect the insidious nature of biliary ileus, which may mimic other causes of intestinal obstruction, delaying diagnosis. Although abdominal ultrasound can reveal pneumobilia, impacted gallstones and fistulas, its effectiveness is limited by the superimposition of intestinal gas. Computed tomography (CT) stood out as the most effective diagnostic method, showing a sensitivity greater than 90% and a specificity close to 100%. In this patient, CT identified intestinal obstruction caused by a foreign body in the distal ileum, which allowed planning a precise and targeted surgical approach.(7, 8, 9)

Surgical treatment of biliary ileus continues to be a topic of debate, with three main approaches:

1. Enterolithotomy: Consists in the removal of the stone through an incision in the affected bowel, leaving the

bilioenteric fistula to close spontaneously. This option is less invasive and is associated with less mortality, which is why it is recommended in high-risk patients or those with significant comorbidities (10, 11).

2. One-stage surgery: Includes enterolithotomy, cholecystectomy and fistula closure in the same procedure. This approach reduces the risk of recurrence of biliary ileus, but carries a higher mortality and risk of complications, particularly in older patients or those with compromised general condition. (10, 11)

3. Two-stage surgery: Enterolithotomy is performed initially to relieve the intestinal obstruction, followed by cholecystectomy and closure of the fistula in a second stage, once the patient has stabilized and the acute inflammatory process has passed. (10, 12)

In this case, isolated enterolithotomy was chosen, without cholecystectomy or closure of the fistula, which allowed a rapid postoperative recovery and a relatively short hospital stay. This approach was chosen because of the patient's clinical status, the absence of acute cholecystitis and sepsis. The decision not to address the bilioenteric fistula was based on evidence that many fistulas close spontaneously after resolution of the obstruction. In addition, manipulation of the fistulous area and cholecystectomy in a patient without acute inflammation could have increased the risk of complications, given the presence of chronic inflammatory adhesions.(12)

CONCLUSION

Barnard's syndrome, although rare, should be considered in patients with bowel obstruction and a history of cholelithiasis, especially in older adults. CT is essential for preoperative diagnosis, allowing adequate surgical planning. Isolated enterolithotomy is a safe and effective option in cases without acute cholecystitis or septic complications, as demonstrated in this patient with favorable postoperative evolution. The choice of surgical approach should be individualized, considering the clinical status of the patient and the presence of comorbidities. This report contributes to the understanding of this rare pathology and supports decision making in its surgical management.

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